
Deliverable D-WP2.3 – Common framework of One Health Surveillance¹

OHEJP JIP MATRIX – WP2

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INIA, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 32-FHI, 33-
NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 41-SVA

¹ Original title: Common framework of OHS surveillance

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D-WP2.3 Common framework of One Health Surveillance – Original title: Common framework of OHS surveillance		
WP and task	WP2-T4: Identify commonalities across the tracks, to propose a common OHS framework when applicable		
Leader	30-RIVM, 13-SSI		
Other contributors	1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 16-INIA, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 41-SVA		
Due month of the deliverable	M58		
Actual submission month	M58		
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 24-Nov-22		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>See updated Grant Agreement</i>		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>	
	National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>		
	EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WHO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
	Other international stakeholder(s): as per OHJEP dissemination plans		
	Social Media: n.a.		
	Other recipient(s): n.a.		

COMMON FRAMEWORK OF OHS SURVEILLANCE

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Introduction

The [One Health European Joint programme \(OHEJP\)](#) Joint Integrative Project (JIP) “[MATRIX: Connecting dimensions in One-Health surveillance](#)” aims to interconnect and strengthen cross-sectorial One Health programmes existing in Europe. This includes animal health, public health and food safety sectors and surveillance systems in order to advance in the practical implementation of One Health Surveillance (OHS). Rather than starting from scratch, MATRIX aims to optimize existing resources to create synergies across the various sectors. The project has produced and/or promoted various solutions for OHS tailored to European countries wanting to design, develop, and implement OHS. This was done in context of four hazards, also known as hazard tracks, and these were *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella*, *Listeria* and emerging hazards.

The thought behind a good functioning OHS system is the opportunity to monitor trends in, between and across the sectors, and get a better understanding of the disease burden. It also can be used as an early warning system with all sectors already involved which supports quicker detection and subsequently outbreak investigation and response.

In most European countries, efforts have already been made to set up a OHS system. In other tasks within MATRIX Work Package 2 (WP2), which focuses on best practices and multi-sectorial collaboration, information on these existing systems have been gathered. In short: in Task 1, the surveillance chain across all sectors was mapped for each of the four hazard-tracks; Task 2 focussed on identifying cross-sectorial surveillance chain linkages to be used for integrated OHS systems; Task 3 described hazard-specific best practices for multi-sectorial collaboration. The results of Task 1 and 2 can be found in [Deliverable 2.1](#) and Task 3 in [Deliverable 2.2](#). Assembling and distributing this knowledge could help countries when setting up or improving OHS systems. The aim of this deliverable is to review and further extend the deliverables and knowledge gained within MATRIX WP2. In doing this, WP 2.4 proposes a Common OHS Framework based on commonalities observed across various hazards in different countries. This framework included both a common map of the OHS systems in place among represented countries as well as a brief overview of best practices applicable to any hazard. Together, these two components make up the common OHS framework.

General One Health Surveillance Chain Map

The general OHS chain map component of the Common OHS Framework was derived from MATRIX WP2, Task 1, which aimed to map OHS systems across sectors and disciplines for the four different hazards in as many countries as possible. In MATRIX deliverable D-WP2.¹², the surveillance chains for all hazards were described based upon survey data collected from eight countries by the working group. Each hazard was investigated in the different sectors involved in surveillance activities in a specific food chain: *Salmonella* was investigated in pork meat, *Campylobacter* in poultry meat, and *Listeria* in dairy products. To address the emerging threats, the example of Hepatitis E in wild boar meat was used, with four different countries (Norway, the Netherlands, Portugal and Italy) reporting on the structure and functionality of their respective systems. The Hepatitis E surveillance chain maps were often significantly less detailed and developed when compared to the other hazards used in this exercise. This was most likely due to the emerging nature of the hazard and relative infancy of the systems being described, making it difficult to summarize and determine any commonalities between countries. Therefore, Hepatitis E and the emerging threat hazard track were excluded from the general OHS chain map, which instead focused on *Salmonella* in five countries (France, Germany, Norway, Spain and United Kingdom), *Campylobacter* in three countries (France, Germany and Norway), and *Listeria* in two countries (Italy and Norway), for a total of 10 maps.

Methods

To create a general OHS chain map, the 10 aforementioned maps were summarized and compared in a stepwise fashion (see **Figure 1**). First, the surveillance chain maps for each hazard were analysed and elements that the majority of systems had in common were recorded to create a combined map per hazard. This map utilized the same format as the country specific maps, to ensure continuity across the maps and easy readership. Then, the now three hazard specific combined maps were analysed and summarized, based on commonalities present in the majority of the maps, to make one general OHS chain map.

Figure 1. Stepwise scheme of developing the general OHS chain map

The general OHS chain map is presented in Figure 2 and is a simplification of the reported structure of OHS in European countries. It should therefore be interpreted with the disclaimer that each country, context, and hazard will alter the way the map is to be interpreted by the user. OHS is not a “one size fits all” concept. Rather, the objective of the general OHS chain map is to provide a common starting place for countries interested in OHS that can be expanded upon according to the currently available requirements and resources.

²MATRIX Deliverable 2.1 can be found here: <https://zenodo.org/record/6406150#.Y06nBHZBw2x>

Interpreting the General One Health Surveillance Chain Map

Sectors and Surveillance stages

The map presents the Animal Health, Food Safety, and Public Health sectors and the respective stages of the relevant surveillance chains, which include the following:

- Primary Production – hatcheries, farms, and other livestock and animal production
- Processing and Distribution – animal transport, slaughterhouse, processing, distribution, and retail
- General Public – consumption and human health

Sampling Contexts

In the initial mapping exercise from MATRIX WP2 Task 1, 12 sampling contexts that could potentially be a part of the surveillance chain were identified. These 12 sampling contexts are listed in a legend in the general OHS chain map as well, though only sampling contexts present in the majority of the country maps per hazard track are listed in the grey circles. The sole commonality in sampling context between the sectors in the final general OHS chain map is “6 - Outbreak Investigation”.

Laboratory Methods

A range of different laboratory methods are used within OHS. The appropriate methods to utilize for any specific hazard will depend on, among other things, the aim of the testing, the speed test results are needed, and the level of details about the pathogen needed. Therefore, the laboratory methods reported in the general OHS chain map are not pathogen specific, nor do they account for country specific laboratory capacities and capabilities. Users should also take national and international standards and protocols into account when choosing the appropriate laboratory methods. Furthermore, methods and techniques can develop over time in general and specific hazards, which should be closely followed.

Limitations

A limitation of this general OHS chain map is the absence of the environmental sector. The MATRIX project does not place specific focus on this sector, hence is not included in the surveillance chain maps. Nevertheless, environmental health is considered an important component of One Health, especially as surveillance in the environmental sector can occur at many steps of the food chain. Therefore, it should be taken into consideration whenever possible when adopting a One Health approach.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830

Common Framework for One Health Surveillance

INVESTIGATED FOOD CHAIN

- SAMPLING CONTEXTS**
- 1 – Baseline survey
 - 2 – Epidemiological study
 - 3 – Monitoring programme
 - 4 – Official control programme
 - 5 – Own check
 - 6 – Outbreak investigation
 - 7 – Research
 - 8 – In case of increased mortality
 - 9 – Hospital data collection system
 - 10 – Industrial accreditation schemes
 - 11 – Clinical study
 - 12 – Antimicrobial resistance monitoring

Figure 2. General One Health Surveillance Chain Map

Common One Health Surveillance Best Practices

In MATRIX Deliverable D-WP2.2³, best practices regarding OHS for each of the MATRIX hazard tracks were described. These best practices were considered from the perspective of three different surveillance purposes: measuring the levels and temporal trends of exposure and burden of disease, supporting early detection and response to outbreaks, and identifying risk factors to implement control measures. Additionally, best practices were presented for four operational One Health activities: Data collection, Data sharing, Data analysis and interpretation, and Results dissemination. For the common OHS framework presented in this current deliverable, the best practices for these four areas were reviewed and summarized transcending the hazard tracks to give a generalizable set of practices to consider when designing, developing and implementing an OHS system.

Methods

To create the collection of Common Best Practices presented in **Table 1**, a similar stepwise strategy as with the surveillance chain map was employed, where the best practices for each hazard found in MATRIX D2.2 were summarized and common themes across pathogens were noted. Furthermore, the Hazard Track leaders involved in crafting the original hazard-specific best practices in MATRIX D2.2 were also involved in the process of reviewing the best practices to highlight elements that are applicable across multiple or any hazard. Thus, the Common Best Practices were derived from both a review of the previous deliverable and expert opinion from the Hazard Track leaders.

Interpreting the Common Best Practices

The objective of the Common Best Practices is to guide the user through the design, development and implementation of their own OHS system, from the perspective of data collection, sharing, analysis and interpretation, and dissemination. The best practices aim to inform the user of strategies others have reported using to avoid various challenges and roadblock regarding the four aforementioned activities and to potentially help the users to prioritize how and where to invest available resources.

Limitations

As was the case for the general OHS chain map, the Common Best Practices are presented without taking into account any pathogen specific hurdles that countries may face. Rather, they present a general set of suggestions for users, who should then apply them to the context within which the OHS system is in place. There is no official way to conduct OHS and these Common Best Practices are a list of suggestions based upon the experiences and findings found within MATRIX.

Overall Conclusion

The previous two MATRIX WP2 deliverables reviewed in this task provided the knowledge used to create the Common OHS Framework presented in this deliverable.

A general OHS chain map transcending specific hazards was constructed based on the results of MATRIX Deliverable D2.1. It should be considered a rough and general template, which can be used as baseline when constructing or reviewing an existing OHS system. When additional sectors and/or stakeholders are identified as relevant for an OHS, regardless of their inclusion in this framework, it is always recommended to include them in the OHS system. Although the general OHS chain map has an apparent focus on laboratory surveillance, both microbiological and epidemiological approaches and results are needed as together they form an OHS system. In MATRIX Deliverable D2.2, best practices within a functioning OHS system were described. Regardless of the hazard of interest, it is important that sectors and stakeholders collaborate, harmonize, communicate and share data and other information within the OHS system. A collaborative effort from multiple sectors would indeed improve results coming from surveillance activities already in place in each field and help to achieve the best possible benefits for all actors.

³ MATRIX Deliverable 2.2 can be found here: <https://zenodo.org/record/7053387#.Y06nCHZBw2w>

Table 1. Common Best Practices for each operational One Health activity

Data Collection	Data Sharing
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Though the definition of roles and responsibilities can be complex, good relationships between all actors will maximise data collected • Target population, sample size, frequency, strategy, location and timing depend on the purpose of testing, the sector, and legislation • Take seasonality into account regarding contamination and infection of both animals and humans • Harmonize definitions to ensure sectors "speak the same language". Otherwise, share case definitions between sectors • Clearly define the diagnostic protocols used in different sectors, including a list of comparable methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An anonymised ID optimizes data sharing and clear population definitions are key to analysis/evaluation activities • Animal and food production volumes and food sales data can be of relevance for outbreak investigation and/or exposure assessment • Necessary data differs per purpose and could consist of prevalence data, concentration of pathogens, incidence data, and morbidity/mortality • Detection is the main focus, although enumeration gives extra information. Typing (especially WGS) becomes more important in helping to detect and define clusters/outbreaks • Some metadata is always needed when sharing data, raw or aggregated and the sampling plan should be transparent. • Frequent and early sharing is key for swift and coordinated outbreak response • Data sharing between public and private sector is highly relevant
Data Analysis/Interpretation	Data Dissemination
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is essential that the research questions analysed are in line with the contexts of the sampling and the data availability • Source attribution and dose-response are useful tools within risk assessment • Skills in statistical/mathematical modelling and bioinformatics within the team is key • When possible, joint data analyses between the public and private sectors should be performed • Mapping the results can be helpful – the use of dashboards could be considered when user interactions are expected, but could introduce misinterpretations as general public and experts are not aware of the specifics regarding the data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination meetings help to ensure a common understanding of context and data, particularly during outbreak investigations • Joint dissemination of results between the public and private sectors is preferred, especially when the different sectors may have different priorities. Coordination and awareness on communications is very important to avoid mixed and/or contradictory messages • External communication can have different forms depending on the audience and overall aim • In the case of real or suspected outbreaks, communication with decision-makers is essential